

MAGICAL MEANS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LITERARY FAIRY TALES

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Magical means play a significant role in both Uzbek and English literary fairy tales, adding an element of wonder, mystery, and enchantment to the stories. In Uzbek literary fairy tales, magical means are often intertwined with elements of folklore, mythology, and traditional beliefs. These tales may feature magical creatures such as dragons, genies, or talking animals, as well as enchanted objects like flying carpets or magic lamps.

In English literary fairy tales, magical means are also commonly used to drive the plot and create a sense of fantasy and escapism for readers. Popular magical elements in English fairy tales include spells, curses, potions, and supernatural beings like fairies, witches, and wizards. These magical means often serve as tools for characters to overcome challenges, achieve their goals, or learn important life lessons.

In both Uzbek and English literary fairy tales, magical means can symbolize the power of imagination, the triumph of good over evil, or the possibility of transformation and growth. They can also serve as metaphors for the unpredictable and mysterious aspects of life, inviting readers to explore themes of destiny, fate, and the unknown.

Overall, magical means in Uzbek and English literary fairy tales add depth, intrigue, and a sense of wonder to the stories, captivating audiences of all ages and cultures. Through the use of magical elements, writers can create enchanting worlds that inspire imagination and spark curiosity in readers.

In the context of literary fairy tales, magical means can be understood as narrative devices that introduce supernatural elements into the story, creating a sense of wonder and enchantment. These magical elements often serve multiple functions within the narrative, including advancing the plot, developing characters, and conveying thematic messages.

In Uzbek literary fairy tales, magical means are deeply rooted in the country's rich folklore and cultural traditions. These tales often draw on Uzbek mythology, legends, and beliefs in supernatural beings to weave intricate and fantastical narratives. Magical creatures such as dragons, spirits, and mythical beasts are common in Uzbek fairy tales, embodying both benevolent and malevolent forces that challenge the protagonists and drive the plot forward.

Similarly, in English literary fairy tales, magical means are used to transport readers into fantastical realms where anything is possible. The presence of fairies, witches, and other supernatural beings adds an element of mystery and whimsy to these stories, inviting readers to suspend disbelief and immerse themselves in a world of magic and wonder. Magical objects like enchanted mirrors, talking animals, and powerful talismans also play a significant role in English fairy tales, serving as catalysts for adventure and transformation.

From a theoretical perspective, magical means in Uzbek and English literary fairy tales can be analyzed through the lens of structuralism, psychoanalysis, or cultural studies. Structuralist approaches may focus on the recurring motifs, symbols, and narrative patterns associated with magical elements in fairy tales, revealing underlying themes of power dynamics, transformation, and the supernatural. Psychoanalytic interpretations might explore the psychological significance of magical means as manifestations of desires, fears, or unconscious impulses within the characters.

Cultural studies perspectives could examine how magical means in Uzbek and English literary fairy tales reflect specific cultural values, beliefs, and societal norms. By analyzing the ways in which magic is portrayed in these tales, scholars can uncover deeper insights into the cultural imagination, folklore traditions, and storytelling conventions of each respective culture.

Overall, the use of magical means in Uzbek and English literary fairy tales adds layers of complexity and depth to these timeless stories, inviting readers to explore themes of magic, mystery, and the extraordinary in imaginative and captivating ways.

It is important to study fairy tales in two large pieces according to the form and content, role and level quantity, purpose, tasks of fantastic and fictional fiction. The first verse includes fairy tales on which fictional fictions are based, and the second verse includes fairy tales on which khayotian fictions are based. And the plot of fairy tales, which entered the first fragment into the miraculous second fragment, is vital, describing events and phenomena that may be in it. Both pieces of fairy tales told mainly three purposes. One tells the story of an ideal hero who triumphs against a supernatural force, brings something vulgar and a miraculous bird, animals, and the other mainly marries another hero in love with other princesses or angels, saves one character or another from a difficult situation, finds medicine for a patient, frees Dragons and Giants, and in the third-events and events related to feudal morality, justice, wisdom, The first and

second goal will be realized against the background of Fantastic Fiction. The plot is based on the principle of being or being absent from the idea, that is, it is built on the basis of such supernatural events and phenomena as turning a guy into a monkey, a girl into a fish, a mirror into water, a comb into a grove. The third goal is realized on the basis of life fiction.

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